

Research methodology

Leaf carbohydrate analysis—a simple method for integrating daily canopy photosynthesis

E. A. Conocono, T. L. Setter, and J. A. Egdane, IRRI

Current methods for assessing carbon assimilation require many photosynthesis measurements taken at different times during the day to get an accurate estimate on a daily basis. This is impractical and expensive in terms of labor and equipment, and it is sometimes impossible to do with more than one sample because of intermittent sunny and cloudy periods during the day.

Carbon assimilation during the day will be integrated by the amount of carbohydrate assimilated by tissues. The nonstructural carbohydrate (soluble sugars and starch) that the plant produces during the day can be quantified by taking the difference between plant carbohydrate content at 6 a.m., when little or no photosynthesis has yet occurred, and at 6 p.m., when the plant has undergone photosynthesis for that day. This method may give a better estimate of carbon assimilated during the day compared with photosynthesis measurements taken at one point in time.

We evaluated the relationship between plant carbohydrate content, daily canopy photosynthesis, and irradiance at the panicle initiation stage. The experiment used irrigated, direct seeded IR72. Light was varied using shade nets. Total soluble sugars was analyzed using anthrone reagent and starch by enzymatic hydrolysis with amyloglucosidase followed by glucose oxidase-peroxidase enzymes. Canopy photosynthesis was measured using a Licor 6200 portable photosynthesis system and a canopy frame (80 cm × 80 cm and 130-cm-high) with a removable top and four 120-mm-diameter battery-operated fans to facilitate equilibration and rapid mixing of gas. Each measurement took 15 s and each replicate was measured 3–6 times every 2 h from 6 a.m. to 6 p.m. at four different radiation levels.

1. Total nonstructural carbohydrate profile of stems and leaves during the day. Plants were unshaded and samples taken at 0-2 days after panicle initiation. (error bars = standard deviation)

There is a linear increase in leaf carbohydrates with time (Fig. 1). This trend is not present in stem carbohydrates, meaning that daily canopy assimilation is more related to leaf carbohydrate content than stem carbohydrate content. The stem acts as storage tissue and may contribute up to 40% or more of grain carbohydrates such that diurnal changes in stem carbohydrates will be relative to high background concentrations. In contrast, leaf carbohydrates are at lower concentrations, and sugars are presumably readily mobilized from these tissues. Hence, leaf carbohydrates better reflect the results of current photosynthesis.

A highly significant direct relationship exists between canopy photosynthesis per day and radiation ($r^2 = 1.00^{**}$), as well as between leaf carbohydrates and radiation ($r^2 = 0.99^{**}$) (Fig. 2). When leaf carbohydrate content and daily canopy photosynthesis are compared, we also find a highly significant correlation ($r^2 = 0.99^{**}$). Similar correlations were obtained in two other experiments.

Based on these results, we suggest that leaf carbohydrate analysis is suitable for

2. Correlation between daily canopy photosynthesis, net leaf carbohydrate content, and daily radiation. (error bars = standard deviation)

quantifying daily canopy photosynthesis, especially when conditions do not allow efficient and accurate photosynthesis measurements. ■

A weather-based empirical model to predict rice leaf blast in Thailand

S. B. Calvero, Jr., IRRI; A. Surin, RPRG-Department of Agriculture (DOA), Thailand; O. Pilansinchai, DOA, Thailand; and P. S. Teng, IRRI

Empirical models are important tools in rice disease management, especially in the context of sustainable agriculture. These models can guide farmers in choosing a disease management strategy to prevent an epidemic. For leaf blast, caused by *Pyricularia grisea*, models have been developed in some temperate countries where the disease naturally occurs. However, few of the models have been applied in actual production systems. In tropical countries such as Thailand, development of empirical models for rice blast is still in its early stages.